

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING INFORMATION COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS THROUGH DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

Karimova Nilufar Boltaboyevna

Independent researcher at Tashkent State
Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15088722>

Annotation: This article covers the methodological foundations of the formation and development of information competence in students through the effective use of digital educational technologies. It analyzes the role of interactive methods, platforms and tools in the educational process that serve to develop the skills of searching, analyzing, selecting, processing and presenting information. Also, methodological recommendations are given to increase students' interest in independent learning and skills in working with information through modern digital tools (*Learning Management System, multimedia resources, programs based on artificial intelligence*).

Keywords: information competence, interactive methodology, digital platforms, independent learning, information processing, innovative educational tools.

Introduction.

In a modern information society, one of the main tasks facing the education system is to form the competence of learners to navigate the information flow, identify the necessary information and use it effectively. Especially for students studying in higher education institutions, this competence is of crucial importance not only in the educational process, but also in their professional activities. Therefore, today, the formation of skills to work with information is becoming the center of educational strategies. At a time when digital technologies have penetrated all aspects of our lives, the issue of their effective use in the educational process is extremely relevant. Through interactive lessons, distance learning, artificial intelligence capabilities and digital platforms, it has become possible to form a critical, systematic approach to information in students. With the help of digital educational technologies, not only knowledge is being effectively developed, but also important skills such as searching, analyzing, sorting, processing and presenting information. The relevance of the topic is that as digital technologies are developing, their role in education is also constantly expanding. In this process, the need to form students' information competence on a methodological basis, through well-thought-out approaches, is increasing. Based on this need, this thesis will comprehensively cover the methodology for developing information competence in students through the use of digital educational technologies.

Methodology:

In today's digital age, educational methodology cannot be limited to traditional approaches. Students need to be formed as individuals who can independently navigate the information world, find solutions to problems through digital means, and have critical and creative thinking. Therefore, in this study, the combination of innovative methods, modern technological tools and methodological approaches was chosen as the main methodological criterion for developing information competence in students. In the process of research, empirical data was collected on the basis of pilot studies, and the initial skills of students in

searching, analyzing and presenting digital information were studied. In this regard, questionnaires, tests, observations, and interviews were widely used. Digital platforms such as Moodle, Google Classroom, and Quizizz were introduced into the learning process, and their impact on educational effectiveness was evaluated.

As a methodological approach, interactive teaching methods based on the principles of constructive pedagogy were used. In this case, students were involved in the lesson process not only as recipients of knowledge, but also as active participants. Through gamification, project-based learning, and collaborative work methods, they were formed with an independent approach to information, critical thinking, and creativity skills. These methodological approaches showed that with the purposeful use of digital tools, the level of students' mastery and the culture of working with information significantly increase. It is for this reason that the results of the study are showing their effectiveness not only theoretically, but also in practice.

Literature review:

In recent years, the number of scientific studies conducted on digital technologies and their role in the educational process has been increasing. In particular, the issues of using information and communication technologies in modern education, the formation of digital literacy, and the development of information competence are in the focus of attention of many foreign and domestic researchers.

Globally, research by J. Martin and K. Green interprets information literacy as an integral part of digital culture. In their opinion, the ability of students to work with information independently is one of the main goals of modern education, and the digitalization of the educational process plays an important role in this regard. UNESCO recommendations also indicate the development of digital skills through information and communication technologies as a global education strategy.

Among local studies, the scientific works of E. Abdurahmonov, D. Jo'rayev and Z. Karimova are noteworthy. They developed methodological recommendations for activating student activity, increasing the level of mastery and forming skills in working with information using digital educational technologies. In particular, their in-depth study of the components of information literacy - search, analysis, evaluation and presentation - enriched the scientific basis in this area. Russian researchers such as G. Selevko and I. Lerner have also substantiated the role of innovative methods and modern information environments in education. Their scientific views emphasize the importance of choosing not only technical means, but also pedagogical strategies for the formation of information competence.

The analysis shows that although the approaches to the development of information competence in the scientific literature are different, they all emphasize the need for a purposeful and integrated use of digital tools. However, methodological complexes, software solutions adapted to the national educational context, and monitoring systems in this regard have not yet been fully developed. Therefore, this thesis proposes methodological approaches that serve to fill this gap.

Results:

Based on the research conducted, it was found that the effective use of digital educational technologies contributes to a significant increase in information competence among students. During the pilot study, digital platforms such as Google Classroom, Moodle, Wordwall, Padlet were introduced into the learning process, and through them, students were

actively involved in the processes of independent search, analysis, comparison, selection and presentation of the knowledge they were acquiring. The difference between the initial and final results was especially noticeable in the skills of independent work and critical thinking. The table below shows the level of development of information literacy between the experimental group (students who received education based on digital technologies) and the control group (students who were taught in the traditional way):

1-table.

Indicators	Initial level (%)	Final grade (%)	Growth rate (%)
Searching and sorting information	47% (control), 49% (experience)	58% (control), 82% (experience)	11% / 33%
Analysis and evaluation of information	42% (control), 45% (experience)	55% (control), 80% (experience)	13% / 35%
Critical thinking and inference	38% (control), 40% (experience)	51% (control), 78% (experience)	13% / 38%
Independent use of digital tools	44% (control), 46% (experience)	60% (control), 85% (experience)	16% / 39%
Information presentation (visual/graphic)	41% (control), 43% (experience)	54% (control), 79% (experience)	13% / 36%

The analysis showed that in the group where digital educational technologies were used, an increase in all areas of information literacy was observed. This proves that in an educational environment enriched with interactive tools, students can achieve high results in navigating the flow of information, selecting and using it purposefully.

Conclusion.

Teaching using digital platforms and interactive tools not only increases learning motivation, but also turns the student into an active participant. Therefore, the integration of traditional teaching methods with modern technologies is one of the most effective approaches to the formation of information literacy. It was also found out based on the results of the study that the development of information literacy is closely related not only to technical means, but also to the creation of an educational environment focused on a correctly selected pedagogical approach, creative methods, project and collaborative work. In conclusion, through the proper use of digital educational technologies, students can be trained as independent, critical-thinking professionals who can navigate freely in the modern information space.

References:

- 1.Abdurahmonov E., Jo'rayev D. Ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar. – Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2020.
- 2.Karimova Z. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari va ta'lim sifati. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi, 2019.
- 3.Selevko G.K. Pedagogik texnologiyalar ensiklopediyasi. – Moskva: Pedagogika, 2006.
- 4.Martin J., Green K. Digital Literacy and Higher Education: A Global Perspective. – Journal of Educational Technology, 2018, Vol. 15, No. 2.

- 5.UNESCO. Media and Information Literacy: Curriculum for Teachers. – Paris: UNESCO Publishing, 2013.
- 6.Lerner I.Ya. Didaktik asoslar: o'quvchilarda muammoli fikrlashni shakllantirish. – Moskva: Znanie, 1994.
- 7.Karimova N. B. Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari vositasida talabalarning axborot kompetentligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik xususiyatlari // "Badiiy ta'lim va pedagogika" ilmiy jurnal. -Toshkent, 2024. -4-son. –B. 146-154. (13.00.00 OAK Rayosatining 355/5-son qarori. 07.06.2024).
- 8.Karimova N. B. Talabalarda axborot kompetentligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik xususiyatlari // "Urganch davlat pedagogika instituti axborotnomasi" ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal. -Urganch, 2025. -1-son. –B. 161-167. (13.00.00 OAK Rayosatining 361-son qarori. 27.09.2024).
- 9.Karimova N. B. Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari vositasida talabalarning axborot kompetentligini rivojlantirish // "Inter Education & Global Study" ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal. -Buxoro, 2024. -8-son. –B. 306-314. (13.00.00 OAK Rayosatining 350-son qarori. 31.01.2024).
- 10.Karimova N. B. Talabalarda axborot kompetentligini rivojlantirishning metodik konseptual asoslari // "Inter Education & Global Study" ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal. -Buxoro, 2024. -10-son. –B. 130-136. (13.00.00 OAK Rayosatining 350-son qarori. 31.01.2024).
- 11.Karimova N. B. Talabalarda axborot kompetentligini rivojlantirishning metodik konseptual asoslari // "Inter Education & Global Study" ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal. -Buxoro, 2024. -10-son. –B. 130-136. (13.00.00 OAK Rayosatining 350-son qarori. 31.01.2024).